

Rice domestication decreases tolerance for yellow stem borer *Scirpophaga incertulas*

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The yellow stem borer *Scirpophaga incertulas* (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae) is an important pest of irrigated rice in Asia because it attacks all stages of the crop (Bandong and Litsinger 2005). Yield loss due to *S. incertulas* has been estimated to range from 5% to 10% (Elazegui et al 1993, Pathak and Khan 1994, Islam and Karim 1997), but it can be as high as 20% in certain regions and on particular varieties (Catling et al 1987, Islam 1990). Larval tunneling during the vegetative stage results in “deadhearts,” while feeding during the reproductive stage results in “whiteheads” or dried and unfilled panicles. Whiteheads, not deadhearts, are the major cause of yield loss (Catling et al 1987, Viajante and Heinrichs 1987, Taylor 1988, Bandong and Litsinger 2005). *Scirpophaga incertulas* is difficult to control because larval tunneling reduces the number of pest management options. Standard plant resistance screening measures at IRRI have focused on plant tolerance, which is a plant’s ability to withstand pest damage while supporting the same levels of pest abundance that would damage a susceptible plant. Despite extensive screening for stem borer resistance, no accessions have been found with tolerance during the reproductive stage (Heinrichs 1988), the period when larval damage most severely affects yield (Bandong and Litsinger 2005).

Wild relatives of agricultural crops are a promising source of resistance because of their long coevolutionary history with insect herbivores and because they retain traits that were lost during the domestication process (Chen and Welter 2005). *Oryza sativa* is clearly less genetically diverse than its wild progenitor *O. rufipogon* (Dally and Second 1990, Sano and Sano 1990, Sun et al 2001). There is also some evidence that *O. rufipogon* is more tolerant of stem borers. In a common garden study, *S. incertulas* densities were lower in plots of *O. rufipogon* than in cultivated rice (Y. Chen, unpubl. data). *Oryza* spp. have been found to be tolerant of stem borers during the vegetative stage (Zaheruddeen and Prakasa Rao 1983, Romena and Heinrichs 1989, Romena et al 1989, Padhi and Sen 2002), so there may be tolerance during the reproductive stage.

The standard screening test for *S. incertulas* tolerance does not differentiate between the vegetative and reproductive stage (Heinrichs et al 1985). Although standard screening tests are adequate for estimating deadhearts during the vegetative phase, the considerable phenological variation among accessions during the reproductive phase can inflate the screening error. Tiller phenology strongly influences larval feeding location and the likelihood of whitehead or deadheart damage. Stem borer larvae are more likely

to attack booting reproductive tillers than vegetative tillers, but ripening tillers are no longer vulnerable to damage (Chen and Romena 2006). Therefore, tolerance scores are inflated if larvae are introduced onto plants too early or too late. Traits associated with tolerance such as stem toughness and silica content are not effective during the reproductive stage because the larvae crawl in between the panicle leaf sheaths to reach the panicle (Chen and Romena 2006). Therefore, plant phenology should be closely monitored when screening for stem borer tolerance during the reproductive stage.

In this study, we use a new screening technique to assess tolerance during the reproductive stage. Although it is considerably more labor intensive, it strongly improves data quality. We use these new methods to (1) determine whether crop domestication has reduced tolerance for *S. incertulas*, (2) determine whether there is variation in tolerance for *S. incertulas* during the reproductive stage, and (3) identify tolerant accessions.

Twenty-one wild accessions and 16 accessions of cultivated rice seeds were requested from the Genetic Resources Center at IRRI (Table 1). Some of the test accessions were chosen because they were previously reported to be tolerant during the reproductive stage (Khan et al 1991). The rice was planted in September

because a short daylength was needed to stimulate reproduction of the wild rice. The seeds were sown directly in a seedbox with fine soil. At 15 d, seedlings were transplanted into a concrete bed in a screenhouse at IRRI, Los Baños, Philippines. Groups of 10 plants from each accession were grown 40 cm apart in a randomized block design. We did not detect a significant block effect, so each accession could be considered to be replicated over 30 plants. Fertilizer was applied at 60 kg N ha⁻¹ 1 wk after transplanting. We rescreened nine accessions of wild rice in 2 consecutive years to assess the reliability of our screening process.

At 45 d after seeding, we started monitoring the plants for panicle development, especially the early-maturing and photoperiod-sensitive varieties. When the panicle was about 1 mm in length, we estimated that it would take 23–25 d until heading because it takes about 30 d from the start of panicle initiation to heading (Yoshida 1981). Plants were infested with larvae when at least 60% of the tillers were booting. Moths were collected every few days for 2 wk after panicle initiation to ensure that larval infestation was timed properly. Using a fine camel-hair brush, we placed three first-instar larvae on each tiller of the booting plants. An alternative method would be to introduce a fixed cohort on each plant, and then count the total number of damaged tillers (K.L. Heong, pers. commun.). This would be in line with the definition of plant tolerance, which is to compare damage between plants carrying the same herbivore load. However, because the number of tillers varies widely between cultivated and wild rice accessions, we standardized the number of larvae

per stem, resulting in a higher herbivore load on the wild plants. This should be considered when evaluating damage across accessions. All plants were harvested 15 d after infestation and stored at 10 °C until they were dissected.

During dissection, we counted the number of tillers and classified the phenological stage of each tiller (tillering, panicle initiation, booting, heading, flowering, milking, hard dough, and ripening) according to Yoshida (1981). Based on our estimation of the amount of time required for tiller maturation, tillers that were in the heading, milking, ripening, and hard dough stages had been exposed to larvae in the susceptible stages (panicle initiation, booting, and flowering). This allowed us to determine the number of tillers exposed during the window of susceptibility. Each tiller was examined for feeding damage and damage was classified into the following categories: partially sterile panicles, highly sterile panicles, deadheart, and whitehead. Sterile panicles and whiteheads were grouped jointly as damaged tillers.

There was considerable variation in plant phenology, particularly for the wild rice accessions (Table 1). We calculated several indices to account for this variation: total number of tillers, proportion of reproductive tillers, proportion of damaged tillers over total tillers, proportion of damaged tillers over ripening tillers, proportion of whiteheads over total tillers, and proportion of whiteheads over ripening tillers. These different statistics were calculated to demonstrate the biases of the more conventional index of whitehead number/total tillers. The proportion of damaged and whitehead tillers over ripening tillers was the most appropriate

measure for estimating damage during the window of susceptibility. For cultivated accessions, sterile tillers were exclusively due to larval feeding, whereas sterile tillers on wild plants were mostly due to incomplete pollination. As a consequence, the number of damaged (sterile and whitehead) tillers was overestimated for wild rice but accurate for cultivated rice.

We used an ANOVA test to determine whether the number of tillers differed between cultivated and wild accessions, and whether the damaged tillers/ripening tillers and whiteheads/ripening tillers differed between species and among accessions. We also tested whether damaged tillers/total tillers and whiteheads/total tillers differed among accessions and between wild and cultivated accessions. To identify tolerant accessions, we set the upper tolerance to 30% damage or 30% whiteheads to reproductive tillers. For each accession, we also used a linear regression to test the relationship between tiller number and tiller damage. The linear regression is a useful way to describe damage risk with increasing number of tillers, while treating each accession as a population of plants. Certainly, there could be considerable among-plant variation within each wild accession. Highly susceptible tillers should have a 1:1 relationship between the number of tillers and the number of damaged tillers. All statistical tests were performed in JMP 5 (SAS Institute 2003).

The accessions showed considerable variation in number of tillers and proportion of ripening tillers (Table 1). Crop domestication has reduced the number of tillers by close to 40%. Although the average wild accession had

Table 1. Plant growth and tolerance for stem borer herbivory. From left, columns indicate (av ± SE) tillers per plant, proportion of reproductive tillers, total damaged tillers, total whiteheads, proportion of damaged tillers to total tillers, proportion of damaged tillers to reproductive tillers, proportion of whiteheads to total tillers, and proportion of whiteheads to reproductive tillers. Both sterile panicles and whiteheads were classified as damaged tillers. Bold numbers indicate accessions with less than 30% damage, indicating tolerance for *S. incertulas*.

Variety/accession	Tillers per plant (no.)	Proportion of reproductive tillers	Total damaged tillers (no.)	Total whiteheads (no.)	Proportion of damaged tillers to total tillers	Proportion of damaged tillers to reproductive tillers	Proportion of whiteheads to total tillers	Proportion of whiteheads to reproductive tillers
Azmil 85	14.87 ± 0.92	0.97 ± 0.01	12.93 ± 0.92	3.88 ± 0.77	0.89 ± 0.03	0.91 ± 0.03	0.2 ± 0.03	0.2 ± 0.03
BMT53 R 3536	31.3 ± 1.48	0.84 ± 0.02	25.17 ± 1.35	19.47 ± 1.29	0.80 ± 0.02	0.96 ± 0.01	0.61 ± 0.02	0.74 ± 0.03
Ballocok	20.23 ± 0.66	0.88 ± 0.03	11.17 ± 1.00	3.68 ± 0.46	0.55 ± 0.05	0.63 ± 0.05	0.17 ± 0.02	0.21 ± 0.03
CI 1240	21.07 ± 1.11	0.88 ± 0.03	18.23 ± 1.31	11.57 ± 1.16	0.84 ± 0.03	0.95 ± 0.02	0.54 ± 0.04	0.62 ± 0.04
CI 27-4	19.57 ± 1.4	0.88 ± 0.02	16.47 ± 1.76	8.00 ± 0.98	0.78 ± 0.05	0.88 ± 0.04	0.39 ± 0.03	0.46 ± 0.04
CI 5339	52.5 ± 2.89	0.84 ± 0.03	38.53 ± 2.81	11.00 ± 1.02	0.72 ± 0.03	0.86 ± 0.02	0.21 ± 0.02	0.26 ± 0.02
Chianan 2	15.37 ± 0.8	0.95 ± 0.02	12.91 ± 0.88	10.77 ± 0.6	0.9 ± 0.02	0.94 ± 0.02	0.72 ± 0.03	0.76 ± 0.03
China 97-35-2	31 ± 1.44	0.96 ± 0.01	25.73 ± 1.69	7.14 ± 1.09	0.81 ± 0.03	0.85 ± 0.03	0.21 ± 0.03	0.22 ± 0.03
Debrax	7.83 ± 0.55	0.72 ± 0.05	5.66 ± 0.50	3.42 ± 0.35	0.68 ± 0.05	0.96 ± 0.02	0.37 ± 0.04	0.55 ± 0.06
Inilang-ilang	9.57 ± 0.85	0.95 ± 0.02	8.5 ± 0.94	4.18 ± 0.53	0.86 ± 0.04	0.91 ± 0.03	0.39 ± 0.04	0.42 ± 0.05
K Askam 36-14	10.78 ± 0.81	0.62 ± 0.04	4.15 ± 0.48	3.88 ± 0.43	0.37 ± 0.04	0.61 ± 0.05	0.35 ± 0.03	0.58 ± 0.05
Rexoro	13.87 ± 0.66	0.93 ± 0.02	11.97 ± 0.60	5.14 ± 0.58	0.87 ± 0.02	0.94 ± 0.04	0.35 ± 0.04	0.38 ± 0.04
Su-yai 20	25.5 ± 1.19	0.61 ± 0.02	7.82 ± 0.83	5.46 ± 0.67	0.28 ± 0.03	0.45 ± 0.05	0.19 ± 0.02	0.32 ± 0.03
Szu-miao	32.21 ± 1.81	0.86 ± 0.02	16.1 ± 1.23	7.83 ± 0.8	0.50 ± 0.03	0.59 ± 0.03	0.24 ± 0.02	0.29 ± 0.02
TKM6	32.03 ± 1.54	0.85 ± 0.02	19.9 ± 1.00	7.79 ± 0.82	0.63 ± 0.02	0.74 ± 0.02	0.22 ± 0.02	0.26 ± 0.03
Taitung 16	17.57 ± 1.22	0.74 ± 0.04	11.67 ± 1.21	8.72 ± 1.07	0.63 ± 0.03	0.87 ± 0.02	0.45 ± 0.04	0.62 ± 0.05
100926 <i>O. rufipogon</i>	28.33 ± 2.13	0.41 ± 0.05	9.43 ± 1.19	6.96 ± 0.72	0.32 ± 0.05	0.74 ± 0.05	0.21 ± 0.03	0.54 ± 0.06
103814 <i>O. nivara</i> / <i>O. rufipogon</i>	18.7 ± 1.7	0.44 ± 0.06	10.74 ± 1.62	6.36 ± 1.11	0.43 ± 0.07	0.91 ± 0.06	0.23 ± 0.04	0.57 ± 0.07
103419 <i>O. nivara</i>	19.67 ± 1.32	0.68 ± 0.04	11.7 ± 1.04	7.17 ± 0.63	0.62 ± 0.04	0.90 ± 0.04	0.39 ± 0.03	0.59 ± 0.04
103823 <i>O. rufipogon</i>	19.85 ± 2.96	0.41 ± 0.07	10.73 ± 2.17	6.87 ± 1.61	0.38 ± 0.07	0.91 ± 0.05	0.24 ± 0.05	0.63 ± 0.07
103830 <i>O. nivara</i>	25.53 ± 0.88	0.78 ± 0.03	16.47 ± 1.07	5.97 ± 0.63	0.64 ± 0.04	0.82 ± 0.03	0.22 ± 0.02	0.3 ± 0.04
103837 <i>O. nivara</i>	27.43 ± 1.29	0.86 ± 0.03	21.07 ± 1.47	7.07 ± 0.95	0.74 ± 0.04	0.87 ± 0.02	0.22 ± 0.03	0.25 ± 0.03
103838 <i>O. nivara</i>	12.37 ± 0.76	0.76 ± 0.03	7.97 ± 0.71	2.52 ± 0.37	0.65 ± 0.04	0.86 ± 0.04	0.15 ± 0.02	0.21 ± 0.03
103840 <i>O. nivara</i>	27.23 ± 1.32	0.94 ± 0.01	25.2 ± 1.34	9.57 ± 0.9	0.93 ± 0.02	0.98 ± 0.02	0.35 ± 0.03	0.37 ± 0.03
103841 <i>O. nivara</i>	23.9 ± 1.06	0.89 ± 0.02	18.7 ± 1.03	6.47 ± 0.65	0.78 ± 0.03	0.88 ± 0.02	0.26 ± 0.02	0.3 ± 0.03
103842 <i>O. nivara</i>	16.87 ± 0.74	0.93 ± 0.02	14.3 ± 0.77	3.63 ± 0.49	0.85 ± 0.03	0.92 ± 0.02	0.17 ± 0.02	0.18 ± 0.03
103844 <i>O. rufipogon</i>	21.53 ± 1.43	0.54 ± 0.06	10.07 ± 1.42	4.17 ± 0.53	0.50 ± 0.06	0.92 ± 0.04	0.22 ± 0.03	0.53 ± 0.07
103849 <i>O. rufipogon</i>	23.6 ± 1.76	0.87 ± 0.03	18.67 ± 1.55	6 ± 1.31	0.79 ± 0.04	0.91 ± 0.03	0.23 ± 0.04	0.29 ± 0.05
104056 <i>O. rufipogon</i> / <i>O. nivara</i>	26.8 ± 1.74	0.61 ± 0.05	14 ± 1.60	7.83 ± 1.49	0.50 ± 0.05	0.82 ± 0.05	0.22 ± 0.04	0.34 ± 0.05
103814 <i>O. nivara</i> / <i>O. rufipogon</i>	37.27 ± 3.33	0.53 ± 0.06	6.76 ± 1.43	6.76 ± 1.43	0.15 ± 0.03	0.31 ± 0.06	0.15 ± 0.03	0.31 ± 0.06
103830 <i>O. nivara</i>	30.67 ± 1.88	0.97 ± 0.01	10.5 ± 0.70	10.5 ± 0.7	0.36 ± 0.02	0.36 ± 0.02	0.36 ± 0.02	0.36 ± 0.02
103837 <i>O. nivara</i>	26.83 ± 2.43	0.98 ± 0.01	5.96 ± 0.72	5.96 ± 0.72	0.18 ± 0.03	0.19 ± 0.03	0.18 ± 0.03	0.19 ± 0.03
103838 <i>O. nivara</i>	27.43 ± 3.18	0.60 ± 0.05	7.25 ± 1.49	7.25 ± 1.49	0.22 ± 0.03	0.42 ± 0.05	0.22 ± 0.03	0.42 ± 0.05
103839 <i>O. nivara</i>	34.17 ± 3.24	0.91 ± 0.02	7.69 ± 0.88	7.69 ± 0.88	0.23 ± 0.03	0.25 ± 0.03	0.23 ± 0.03	0.25 ± 0.03
103840 <i>O. nivara</i>	25.93 ± 1.43	0.92 ± 0.01	9.37 ± 0.69	9.37 ± 0.69	0.38 ± 0.02	0.41 ± 0.03	0.38 ± 0.02	0.41 ± 0.03
103841 <i>O. nivara</i>	29.4 ± 1.87	0.92 ± 0.02	6.27 ± 0.64	6.27 ± 0.64	0.22 ± 0.02	0.24 ± 0.02	0.22 ± 0.02	0.24 ± 0.02
103842 <i>O. nivara</i> / <i>O. sativa</i>	23.43 ± 1.37	0.99 ± 0.01	4.73 ± 0.54	4.73 ± 0.54	0.2 ± 0.02	0.21 ± 0.02	0.2 ± 0.02	0.21 ± 0.02
104612 <i>O. nivara</i>	30.47 ± 2.4	0.70 ± 0.04	9.9 ± 1.08	9.9 ± 1.08	0.33 ± 0.03	0.48 ± 0.04	0.33 ± 0.03	0.48 ± 0.04
105409 <i>O. nivara</i>	32.83 ± 3.22	0.61 ± 0.04	10.37 ± 1.37	10.37 ± 1.37	0.32 ± 0.03	0.55 ± 0.04	0.32 ± 0.03	0.55 ± 0.04
105710 <i>O. nivara</i>	24.9 ± 1.34	0.86 ± 0.03	9.93 ± 0.77	9.93 ± 0.77	0.41 ± 0.03	0.48 ± 0.04	0.41 ± 0.03	0.48 ± 0.04
106041 <i>O. nivara</i>	51.43 ± 3.83	0.79 ± 0.02	13.57 ± 1.22	13.57 ± 1.22	0.27 ± 0.02	0.34 ± 0.02	0.27 ± 0.02	0.34 ± 0.02
100926 <i>O. rufipogon</i>	27.97 ± 1.55	0.49 ± 0.05	8.39 ± 0.93	8.39 ± 0.93	0.27 ± 0.03	0.62 ± 0.05	0.27 ± 0.03	0.62 ± 0.05
103844 <i>O. rufipogon</i>	35.68 ± 3.56	0.36 ± 0.05	2.08 ± 0.56	2.08 ± 0.56	0.03 ± 0.01	0.09 ± 0.02	0.03 ± 0.01	0.09 ± 0.02
105349 <i>O. rufipogon</i>	38.93 ± 2.31	0.91 ± 0.02	16.53 ± 1.45	16.53 ± 1.45	0.41 ± 0.03	0.45 ± 0.03	0.41 ± 0.03	0.45 ± 0.03
105554 <i>O. rufipogon</i>	33.07 ± 1.75	0.96 ± 0.01	11.83 ± 1.05	11.83 ± 1.05	0.35 ± 0.02	0.37 ± 0.02	0.35 ± 0.02	0.37 ± 0.02
106039 <i>O. rufipogon</i>	36.3 ± 3.11	0.61 ± 0.06	8.96 ± 1.22	8.96 ± 1.22	0.22 ± 0.03	0.4 ± 0.05	0.22 ± 0.03	0.4 ± 0.05

25.05 ± 0.44 tillers, cultivated accessions averaged 15.95 ± 0.32 tillers ($F_{1, 1344} = 200.35$, $P < 0.0001$). Cultivated accessions had a higher proportion of ripening tillers (0.85 ± 0.01) than wild accessions (0.74 ± 0.01; $F_{1, 1344} = 200.35$, $P < 0.0001$). Given this difference in phenology between species, the proportion of damaged/ripening tillers was a better index for comparing tolerance among accessions and between species.

Rice domestication appears to have lowered plant tolerance for *S. incertulas*. Despite receiving fewer larvae during the screening process, cultivated rice accessions had a higher proportion of damaged/ripening tillers (0.82 ± 0.01) than wild rice accessions (0.58 ± 0.01; $F_{1, 1324} = 191.23$, $P < 0.001$). Cultivated accessions also had a higher proportion of whiteheads/ripening tillers (0.43 ± 0.01) than wild accessions (0.37 ± 0.01; $F_{1, 1324} = 13.62$, $P < 0.01$). Given that estimates of sterility were likely overestimated for wild rice accessions, it was more appropriate to compare the proportion of damaged/ripening tillers for cultivated accessions (0.82 ± 0.01) to whiteheads/ripening tillers for wild accessions (0.37 ± 0.01). In any case, wild accessions exhibited more tolerance for larval damage.

There was significant variation in damaged/ripening tillers among accessions (Table 2; $F_{45, 1280} = 58.82$, $P < 0.0001$). Almost all cultivated accessions had more than 60% of the ripening tillers damaged (Table 1). Only two accessions showed signs of moderate tolerance. Su-yai 20 and Szu-miao had slightly lower levels of damage, with 45% and 59% of the ripening tillers damaged. In contrast, the level of damage on wild rice was much lower. Accessions 103842 and 103837 had

the lowest proportion of whiteheads/ripening tillers, with 18% and 19% of the ripening tillers damaged. Using 30% whitehead damage to ripening tillers as the upper limit, 10 wild accessions showed signs of tolerance for *S. incertulas* (Table 1).

For the subset of wild accessions that was rescreened, we found that the proportion of whiteheads/reproductive tillers was similar between screening trials. On the other hand, there was some variability in the proportion of damaged/reproductive tillers because lower pollination in 2006 led to more sterile panicles (Table 1). For Acc. 103844, screening was not timed accurately with the phenology, leading to a larger difference between screening trials in the proportion of whiteheads/reproductive tillers. Both times it was screened, it had less than 50% reproductive tillers. The other possible cause for the difference between years is that random sampling of a small subset of a diverse population could lead to a different average score. Therefore, it is recommended that screening be repeated several times before selecting a parent for breeding purposes.

Table 1 also demonstrates the importance of linking larval damage with plant phenology. We presented both damage and whiteheads in terms of actual numbers and the proportion of damage. Both sets of information can be used to identify accessions that perform better than others. For instance, Acc. 103844 had very few whiteheads, but this was due to a low proportion of ripening tillers. Similarly, the cultivated accession K Askam 36-14 had relatively low damage to its reproductive tillers (34%), but it also had a lower proportion of reproductive tillers. Although

this accession appeared to be tolerant in this study, it should be rescreened during the booting stage. Therefore, accounting for plant phenology will improve the precision of screening for tolerance for *S. incertulas*.

We found that almost all accessions showed a positive relationship between number of tillers and number of whiteheads or damaged tillers (Table 2). The only accession that did not show a positive relationship was wild rice Acc. 103844, but this was likely due to the low proportion of reproductive tillers during the screening period (Table 1). The positive relationship between total tillers and damaged tillers was much higher for cultivated accessions than for wild accessions, indicating that cultivated tillers were more likely to be damaged. Using the linear regressions estimated for each accession, we predicted the average number of damaged tillers for a plant with 20 tillers. The average wild accession would have 5.01 ± 0.09 damaged tillers, whereas the average cultivated plant would have 13.30 ± 0.25 damaged tillers. Table 2 shows the damage predictions for a plant with 20 tillers using the linear regression generated for each accession. Several wild accessions (Acc. 103849, 104056, 103830, 103837, 103841, and 103842) predicted a particularly low number of whitehead tillers (Table 2). These accessions also showed lower damage in Table 1.

By developing a more reliable screening technique that accounts for plant phenology, we have identified several wild rice donors that are tolerant of *S. incertulas* during the reproductive stage. These accessions could be used to enhance the tolerance of cultivated rice. Our key recom-

Table 2. Accession information and the linear regression predicting the relationship between total tillers and tiller damage. For cultivated accessions, the equations predict tiller damage (sterile and whitehead panicles). For wild accessions, the equations predict the number of whiteheads. The equations were then used to predict the number of affected tillers for a hypothetical plant with 20 tillers. The remaining columns refer to wild or cultivated species, the IRRI International Genetic Resources Center (IRGC) accession number, variety or species name, and geographic region where it was first collected.

Species	IRGC no.	Variety/species name	Origin	Damage prediction	Predicted damage for 20 tillers
Cultivated	89	Chianan 2	Taiwan	Damaged = $0.11 + 0.89$ total tillers	17.91
Cultivated	99	Taitung 16	Taiwan	Damaged = $-4.62 + 0.92$ total tillers	13.78
Cultivated	143	Rexoro	USA	Damaged = $0.98 + 0.79$ total tillers	16.78
Cultivated	237	TKM6	India	Damaged = $5.42 + 0.44$ total tillers	14.22
Cultivated	289	Azmil 85	Philippines	Damaged = $2.41 + 0.71$ total tillers	16.61
Cultivated	558	Ballocok	Philippines	Damaged = $-0.09 + 0.56$ total tillers	11.11
Cultivated	690	Inilang-ilang	Philippines	Damaged = $-1.69 + 1.07$ total tillers	19.71
Cultivated	958	CI 5339	China	Damaged = $-7.38 + 0.87$ total tillers	10.02
Cultivated	1099	K Askam 36-14	China	Damaged = $2.29 + 0.15$ total tillers	5.29
Cultivated	1601	China 97-35-2	China	Damaged = $-6.49 + 1.04$ total tillers	14.31
Cultivated	1796	Debrax	USA	Damaged = $-0.31 + 0.72$ total tillers	14.09
Cultivated	1863	BMT53 R 3536	USA	Damaged = $-0.92 + 0.81$ total tillers	15.28
Cultivated	3465	CI 27-4	Sri Lanka	Damaged = $-6.59 + 1.18$ total tillers	17.01
Cultivated	3466	CI 1240	Sri Lanka	Damaged = $-4.58 + 1.08$ total tillers	17.02
Cultivated	3483	CI 5339	China	Damaged = $-7.38 + 0.8$ total tillers	8.62
Cultivated	7299	Su-yai 20	China	Damaged = $-1.69 + 0.34$ total tillers	5.11
Cultivated	7300	Szu-miao	China	Damaged = $-0.93 + 0.51$ total tillers	9.27
Wild	103419	<i>O. nivara</i>	Sri Lanka	WH = $3.92 + 0.16$ total tillers	7.12
Wild	103823	<i>O. rufipogon</i>	China	WH = $0.94 + 0.21$ total tillers	5.14
Wild	103849	<i>O. rufipogon</i>	India	WH = $-8.03 + 0.59$ total tillers	3.77
Wild	104056	<i>O. rufipogon/O. nivara</i>	China	WH = $-3.55 + 0.36$ total tillers	3.65
Wild	104612	<i>O. nivara</i>	Sri Lanka	WH = $-0.08 + 0.32$ total tillers	6.48
Wild	105349	<i>O. rufipogon</i>	India	WH = $-1.39 + 0.46$ total tillers	7.81
Wild	105409	<i>O. nivara</i>	Sri Lanka	WH = $0.36 + 0.30$ total tillers	6.36
Wild	105554	<i>O. rufipogon</i>	India	WH = $-3.51 + 0.46$ total tillers	5.69
Wild	105710	<i>O. nivara</i>	India	WH = $5.03 + 0.20$ total tillers	9.03
Wild	106039	<i>O. rufipogon</i>	India	WH = $0.52 + 0.21$ total tillers	4.72
Wild	106041	<i>O. nivara</i>	India	WH = $1.99 + 0.23$ total tillers	6.59
Wild	100926	<i>O. rufipogon</i>	Myanmar	WH = $2.89 + 0.10$ total tillers	4.89
Wild	100926	<i>O. rufipogon</i>	Myanmar	WH = $-0.48 + 0.30$ total tillers	5.52
Wild	103814	<i>O. nivara/O. rufipogon</i>	China	WH = $-2.76 + 0.36$ total tillers	4.44
Wild	103814	<i>O. nivara/O. rufipogon</i>	China	WH = $-0.40 + 0.16$ total tillers	2.8
Wild	103830	<i>O. nivara</i>	Bangladesh	WH = $-0.23 + 0.23$ total tillers	4.37
Wild	103830	<i>O. nivara</i>	Bangladesh	WH = $5.49 + 0.16$ total tillers	8.69
Wild	103837	<i>O. nivara</i>	Bangladesh	WH = $-8.34 + 0.53$ total tillers	2.26
Wild	103837	<i>O. nivara</i>	Bangladesh	WH = $0.15 + 0.17$ total tillers	3.55
Wild	103838	<i>O. nivara</i>	Bangladesh	WH = $-8.34 + 0.22$ total tillers	-3.94
Wild	103838	<i>O. nivara</i>	Bangladesh	WH = $-2.33 + 0.33$ total tillers	4.27
Wild	103839	<i>O. nivara</i>	Bangladesh	WH = $-2.72 + 0.14$ total tillers	5.52
Wild	103840	<i>O. nivara</i>	Bangladesh	WH = $-0.21 + 0.36$ total tillers	6.99
Wild	103840	<i>O. nivara</i>	Bangladesh	WH = $0.90 + 0.33$ total tillers	7.5
Wild	103841	<i>O. nivara</i>	Bangladesh	WH = $-3.02 + 0.40$ total tillers	4.98
Wild	103841	<i>O. nivara</i>	Bangladesh	WH = $0.19 + 0.21$ total tillers	4.39
Wild	103842	<i>O. nivara/O. sativa</i>	Bangladesh	WH = $-0.78 + 0.22$ total tillers	3.62
Wild	103842	<i>O. nivara/O. sativa</i>	Bangladesh	WH = $0.42 + 0.18$ total tillers	4.02
Wild	103844	<i>O. rufipogon</i>	Bangladesh	NS	NS
Wild	103844	<i>O. rufipogon</i>	Bangladesh	NS	NS

mendations for modifying the screening technique are to (1) record tiller phenology of each plant during the damage assessment, (2) count the number of ripening and total tillers on each plant, (3) determine the proportion of damaged tillers/ripening tillers and whiteheads/ripening tillers, and (4) assess the relationship between the total number of tillers and the number of damaged tillers for each accession. A linear regression is appropriate because it accounts for considerable variation that can be found among plants within a particular accession. It can also be used as a predictive tool, as we have done here.

Rice domestication has decreased tillering and reduced plant phenological variation (Cai and Morishima 2002). The simplification of plant architecture during domestication and breeding has been linked with a reduction in tolerance for herbivory in other crops (Welter and Steggall 1993). The greater frequency of tolerance in wild accessions provides strong evidence that domestication and selective breeding have reduced the tolerance of rice for *S. incertulas*. The decrease in tiller production increases the relative impact that each *S. incertulas* larva can have on total plant reproductive fitness. Also, the uniformity of flowering further increases the impact of *S. incertulas* on cultivated rice because all of the tillers are in the window of susceptibility at the same time (Chen and Romena 2006). Given that *O. sativa* panicles are larger than *O. rufipogon* panicles (IRRI GRC, unpubl. data), each damaged tiller has a greater impact on plant fitness in cultivated rice. Rice domestication has clearly reduced plant tolerance for stem borer herbivory, but identifying

tolerant accessions opens up new opportunities to study the morphological and biochemical basis of rice tolerance for *S. incertulas* damage during the reproductive stage. These accessions can also be used to begin the long process of breeding for stem borer resistance in rice.

Acknowledgments

The authors gratefully acknowledge Carmen Bernal, Modesto Calica, Reyuel Quintana, Rodante Abas, and Albert Naredo for their contribution to this work. We also thank K.L. Heong for his valuable comments that improved this manuscript.

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